

National Economic Stability and the Strategy of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH)

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ABSTRACT: The economic well-being of any nation depends on its stability, immobility, and constancy which core principle is justice that is emphatically upheld in the Seerah of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) which made it sure that not any part of the society would be deprived of wealth and resources. The Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) promoted free trade, implemented economic reforms, taught people business ethics and set the role of the state in this regard. However, this qualitative study by utilizing interdisciplinary research methodology comprises of historical analysis, textual interpretation, and contemporary socio-economic insights provides viable responses to future challenges, paving the way towards a robust, fair and strengthened economic system. It also gives understanding of those elementary strategies that can be implemented to achieve economic stability within a nation based on the life of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) which provides essential guidance for devising tactics aimed at attaining economic equilibrium within a state. Furthermore, avoiding excessive debt and practicing cautious financial and monetary management are stressed in the Seerah. A framework for the economy that promotes prosperity, equity, and flexibility in the face of adversity can be established by policymakers by placing a strong emphasis on the values of justice, entrepreneurship, social welfare, and commercial prudence.

Key words: Economic Stability, Seerah, Strategies, Market Reforms, Business Ethics, Prohibition of Interest, Foreign Policy, Role of State.

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1. Introduction

Allah Almighty, created this universe, arranged and ornamented it with all things, then created Adam, conferring upon him the position of vicegerent on the Earth. He not only privileged all creatures but also made them submissive to him. Allah says in Qur'an :

“ وَلَقَدْ كَرَّمْنَا بَنِي آدَمَ وَحَمَلْنَاهُمْ فِي الْبَرِّ وَالْبَحْرِ وَرَزَقْنَاهُمْ مِنَ الطَّيِّبَاتِ وَفَضَّلْنَاهُمْ عَلَى كَثِيرٍ مِمَّنْ خَلَقْنَا تَفْضِيلًا¹ ”

We have honoured the sons Of Adam ; provided them With transport on land and sea ; Given them for sustenance things Good and pure ; and conferred On them special favours, Above a great part Of Our Creation.” *

Thus, before the creation of Adam, the wise Creator adorned the earth's surface with the creation of its means of sustenance

” إِنَّ رَبَّكُمْ اللَّهُ الَّذِي خَلَقَ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضَ فِي سِتَّةِ أَيَّامٍ ثُمَّ اسْتَوَىٰ عَلَى الْعَرْشِ يُدِيرُ الْأَمْرَ “²

“Verily your Lord is God, Who created the heavens And the earth in six Days, And is firmly established On the Throne (of authority), Regulating and governing all things.”

After it He Almighty subjected the whole vast universe to the man

وَسَخَّرَ لَكُمْ اللَّيْلَ وَالنَّهَارَ وَالشَّمْسَ وَالْقَمَرَ.³

“He has made subject to you The Night and the Day ; The Sun and the Moon”

The great purpose of this subjugation was to fulfill the divine duty of utilizing these means and resources while benefiting from them. The spread of the offspring of Adam across various regions of the earth and their settlement in diverse circumstances necessitated the advancement of human thought, civilization, and life. In this manner, the Creator did not leave the treasures of the earth and heavens solely at the disposal of unbridled reason; instead, He bound it to the spiritual upbringing, alongside fulfilling bodily needs, to keep its mental faculties on the right path. Thus, from Adam began the chain of prophet hood, culminating in the mission of Muhammad (PBUH).

أَلْيَوْمَ أَكْمَلْتُ لَكُمْ دِينَكُمْ وَأَتَمَمْتُ عَلَيْكُمْ نِعْمَتِي وَرَضِيْتُ لَكُمُ الْإِسْلَامَ دِينًا⁴

“This day have I perfected your religion for you completed my favor upon you and have chosen for you Islam as your religion.”

Thus He Almighty completed the religion not only universally but comprehensively by providing guidance in all aspects of life.

The present era is considered a developed phase in human history as the modern innovations, especially means of communication and transportation, along with messengers and messages, have transformed the world into a global village. Humans are attempting to venture beyond Earth, aiming to settle on Mars. However, the other side of the picture is the significant dilemma of human economy, where despite the rapid and pleasant progress, almost every half-century witnesses an economic crisis. Despite scientific and technological

¹ Al Qur'an, 17 : 7

* Abdullah Yousuf Ali, The Holy Qur'an (Translation of Qur'an) is used for verses of Qur'an in this article.

² Al Qur'an, 10 : 03

³ Al Qur'an, 16 : 12

⁴ Al Qur'an, 05 : 03

advancement, economic downturns persist, showcasing the failure and helplessness of human intellect.⁵

In reality, every individual in society seeks sustenance according to their intentions, preferences, and available means. However, the economic struggles of all members of society are interconnected and dependent on each other, with personal interests inherent within. If these efforts are left at the individual level, such a method may be highly beneficial for some individuals but does not ensure economic stability. For a robust economy, there is a need for a structured and organized economic system that not only coordinates individual efforts at the societal level but also ensures continuous economic development and prosperity through social accountability. This quality is a sign of economic stability.

Since the commencement, the acquisition of sustenance has ever been the goal of humanity along with the desires for the well-being of the social life. Therefore, throughout every era, human intellect has remained vigilant, and various systems prevailed in great empires, among which capitalism and socialism emerged successively. These systems are still prevalent in various states and regions worldwide. However, despite the extensive experiences of past times, these systems have failed to establish the foundations of stable economy.

As mentioned in the above passages, Islam is not just a name for worship methods and religious rituals; rather, it is a comprehensive guide for every aspect of life. This is why the uncivilized and scattered society of Arabia not only became one of the greatest states in the world within a short period but also emerged as the strongest and most stable economy, where the national treasury was brimful and the citizens of the state were also affluent. Before evaluating the economic stability of an Islamic state and the prophetic measures, it is essential to evaluate the manifestations of economic stability.

2. Indicators of Economic Stability

Any economy progressing towards development and stability will be evaluated from two aspects: the National aspect and the Social aspect.

1. Presently, the estimation of economic development from the national aspect can be assessed through the reserves present in the national treasury, the balance of trade, the average rate of long-term increase in raw national production, and its constant trend, the state of the annual budget, and the volume of public welfare projects. If the country possesses abundant reserves of exchange, the inflows and revenues are balanced, expenditures do not exceed incomes, the average rate of increase in raw national production in the long term is high, and its trend is constant, the national income in the annual budget exceeds national expenditure, there is no budget deficit, and a significant

⁵ Bondarenko, Peter. "Five of the World's Most Devastating Financial Crises". Encyclopedia Britannica, 1st Sep. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/story/5-of-the-worlds-most-devastating-financial-crises>. (Accessed 22 October 2024).

amount of funds is allocated for public welfare projects, then these factors indicate economic progress.⁶

2. At the social level, some matters indicate economic stability, such as the progress and welfare of the common people in the state, peace and security, and the economic condition of wealth circulation. If the basic human rights are available to the public, facilities for education and health are accessible, employment opportunities are available, wealth is not confined to the accounts of a few wealthy landlords and major capitalists, business freedom and facilities are available, it indicates economic progress. National peace and security, a decrease in the crime rate, and the provision of justice also indicate stability. Besides, reducing economic disparities between the rich and the poor is the most imperative aspect of economic stability.

3. Islamic Economic System and Its Important Characteristics

With the descent of man on this earth, the process of earning his livelihood started and his economic endeavors in society gave birth to prosperity. Throughout the annals of history, principles and regulations have been established to strengthen the economic sector of human life, which is called the economic system. Although different systems prevailed according to the demands of each era, when we study the economic history described by Western scholars, only two systems seem apparent: capitalist and socialist systems.

The socialist system also declined after its peak in the 1970s, while the capitalist system has been prevalent for centuries. However, during the golden age of the Islamic state from the 7th to the 11th century AD, a prosperous economy and a successful commercial system were prevalent, not only challenging the theory of "Great Gap Thesis" but also labeling it as "Five blank centuries."⁷ This wrong theory was refuted almost half a century later in 2003 by the Muslim scholar Dr. S. M. Ghazanfar in a detailed book entitled "Medieval Islamic Economic Thought: filling the "Great Gap" in European economics". Despite this detailed book, there has been little awareness about the Islamic economic system.

Later, German scholar Benedict Koehler introduced the established and successful economic system of the State of Medina⁸, which was implemented over fifteen hundred years ago in Medina and remained successful for five hundred years, spreading its economic reality throughout the world.

To strengthen the economy, the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) adopted a code of conduct that not only propelled the Arab nomadic tribes ahead of the civilized and powerful empires of the world in the economic field but also sustained their rise in the world for centuries. Before detailing the important characteristics of the Islamic economic system, it is necessary to mention them so that the discussion can be facilitated. However, the important characteristics of the Islamic economic system are as follows:

⁶ "WDI-Economy-world bank <https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/themes/economy.html> (accessed on 22-10-2024).

⁷ Schumpeter - Joseph .A , History of Economic Analysis (Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2006)70

⁸ Koehler. B , Early Islam and Birth of Capitalism (2014)

Islamic Economic Conception

Behind every aspect of life, there is a thought process that influences individual and social spheres of action. Being a religion, Islam provides constant guidance on all aspects of life, emphasizing more on reforming thought and perspective rather than just laws. Therefore, the comprehensive theory it provides regarding business and economy, which are crucial both individually and socially, focuses more on reforming thought and perspective than just laws. The important aspects of which are as follows:

The Concept of Real Ownership

The concept of real possession and proprietorship belongs to Allah Almighty, as in Qur'an Almighty ordained that:⁹ *وَاللَّهُ مِيرَاثُ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ*. "To God belongs the heritage of the heavens and the earth" Indeed Man has been given temporary custodianship under the earth's authority as within worldly affairs, every person has the right to ownership within certain limits and conditions, and they are accountable for both lawful and unlawful use and enjoyment.

Balance of Ethics and Economy

Islam does not contradict and refute the economic endeavors but unlike other economic systems, sustenance and economy is not the purpose of life. Although it is an imperative facet of human life but it is placed under the umbrella of other aspects of life. For a successful life, equilibrium and balance is essential among religion, ethics, politics, society, and economy. Hence, in the Holy Quran, where there prayer and charity are commanded, prayer is mentioned before charity¹⁰ *وَأَقِيمُوا الصَّلَاةَ وَآتُوا الزَّكَاةَ*. "And be steadfast in prayer; practice regular charity"

This sequence is based on great wisdom, as the term "prayer" encompasses religion, ethics, politics, and society, while the term "charity" is used for economy and finances. In contrast to Islam, the capitalist system emphasizes complete freedom, while socialism completely negates it. In the Islamic system, if the balance between ethics and economy is disturbed, economic activity will not be acceptable no matter how beneficial it may seem. Therefore, Islam supports individual freedom in economy except for some prohibited items.

Practical Code of Conduct

Islam is a practical religion which gives its followers not only theoretical framework, but also provides a comprehensive practical code of conduct which diverts economic aspect of life of an individual and nation to success. Salient features of this practical code of conduct are as follows:

The concept of success in individual (private) business transactions

In Islam, ethics have precedence over economy, and the main purpose of commercial and business transactions among individuals is benefit. For this reason, Islamic

⁹ Al Qur'an, 03: 180

¹⁰ Al Qur'an, 02: 43

compassion is observed in economic profits, where it's necessary to disclose the defects and qualities of the goods for sale to the buyer¹¹, and sometimes the buyer is given the option to choose, because trade is a means of mutual benefit. This is why the rank of a truthful and honest merchant is placed after the prophets and the righteous, because unlike other professionals, a merchant deals with a large number of people. However, in the modern era, the term "production" has broadened its scope, encompassing both goods and services.

Concept of Free Market

The principle of a free market system is established in the market, where there are no restrictions on the measures and dealings of producers, what to produce, for whom to produce, and how much to produce, relying on the discretion of sellers and buyers. However, unlike the capitalist system, this freedom is not absolute. There is no room for prohibited production and usurious capital investment.

Determination of Prices

Price determination occurs through the free forces of supply and demand. Unlike the capitalist system, there is no allowance for the individual's ownership or for alliances of business managers that lead to artificial inflation, nor is there government control as in socialism.

Economic Consumption of Capital

Capital is the most vital aspect in production. In Islam, capital is used for the production of goods and services. It is employed in trade, industry, and crafts, and both profit and loss can result from it. In a capitalist system, the capitalist receives compensation in the form of interest. However, the concept of interest is completely prohibited in Islam.¹² يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَأْكُلُوا الرِّبَا أَضْعَافًا مُضَاعَفَةً “O ye who believe! devour not usury doubled and multiplied”

Therefore, its benefits spread throughout society in the form of economic development in fact economic discrepancies are minimalized through the circulation of wealth.

Role of Government

The development of any country is not doable and possible merely through individual efforts, unless government institutions, resources, and authorities do not espouse and take measures with upright intentions. An earnest and honest government can achieve its objectives through the following actions:

Developmental and Public Welfare Works

¹¹ Al-Bukhāri, Abu Abdullah, Muhammad bin Ismā'il, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, "Kitab Al-Buyû", Bāb Idhāa Ba'yn Al-Bayān Wa lam Yaktuma Wa Nasahā , Hadith: 2028, (Al-Matba'ah Al-Kubra Al-Amiriyyah, 1311 AH.).

¹² Al Qur'an, 03 : 130

Besides, defense, justice and in retaining peace, government plays an important and significant role in the spectrum of economic. In addition to implementing crucial developmental and public welfare projects, the provision of finances is also its responsibility. Continuously ongoing welfare and developmental projects in the country signify economic stability as well.

Collection of Zakat, Usher and other Revenues

Zakat and Usher are financial obligations determined by the rate, threshold, and recipients prescribed by Allah. However, organized systems are required for their collection and distribution. Similarly, collection of Jizya and Khiraj from non-Muslims and in unavoidable circumstances and the operation of state systems, the government is responsible for the enforcement, collection, and management of revenues, including the distribution and expenditure of funds.

Accountability System

Although Islam envisions a free market concept, it does not entirely leave it to the discretion of merchants, as sometimes this freedom leads to exploitation and economic downturns. Therefore, the monitoring of rent, monopolies, hoarding, and artificial inflation is also the responsibility of the government.

Hence, after recalling the characteristics of the Islamic economic system, it becomes easy to comprehend how the retrograde Arabs prevailed over the developed and strong empires of Rome and Persia and what were the motives and the causes that the nations touching the acme and the peak of material progress today are unable to find a permanent solution to economic problems which how fourteen hundred years ago, the Arabian Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) achieved that goal.

4. National Economic Stability and The Strategy of The Prophet Muhammad (PBUH)

The gradual revelation of the Quran was based on the principle that it would permanently influence minds and be long-lasting and effective. It was this principle that the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) adopted in establishing a strong economic system in the State of Medina.

In the present era, we often fall into the misconception that interest (riba) is the root cause of all evils, and if it is eliminated, economic stability will robotically be achieved. However, a deep inspection of the Seerah (biography) of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) reveals that the prohibition of interest was the final measure based on this same principle of gradual teachings.¹³

Directive sequence of Prophetic Strategy

¹³ Abu al-Husain Muslim bin al-Hajjaj al-Qushayri, Al-Musnad Al-Sahih, Kitab Al-Hajj, Bāab Hujjat al-Nabi, Hadith: 1218, (Dar Ihyā al-Turath al-Arabi , Beirut 1955).

Medina and Mecca were famous for business from two different angles, as since Mecca was a land without water and vegetation, its people were skilled in trade and sold their goods in markets around the world, while Medina was a city surrounded by gardens and its people were famous for agriculture. Both the Migrants of Mecca and the natives of Medina were skilled in "agriculture and trade", but the Jews were economically stronger in the Arabian Peninsula. They migrated from developed regions like Syria and Palestine and settled here. They were skilled with numerous arts which were completely unfamiliar for Arabs. Their business relations with the world outside the Arabian Peninsula were quite primordial and stable. That is why they had a complete monopoly on the import of grain and the export of dried dates from Medina and Northern Hejaz region.

Hence, after the establishment of the State of Medina, one of the significant objectives was the reformation of the economic sector. When The Prophet (PBUH) migrated to Medina, the economy was under the control of the Jews, all four markets of Medina were occupied by them, they imposed tax on trade in these markets which was not only infirmity for traders but also a burden on consumers in the result of high prices. They also engaged in usurious transactions. Besides of few affluent individuals, almost everyone else was indebted to them. In such circumstances, an immediate prohibition of interest was impossible. Therefore, the Prophet (PBUH) first implemented reforms that strengthened Muslims financially and reduced the influence of Jews in the Medina market. If we analyze His (PBUH) actions historically, we establish systematic economic wisdom and strategy in three stages, which is a pledge of success for every era.

First stage

Establishment of Market and Protection of Merchants' Rights

Each individual cannot fulfill his needs independently; he depends on others. This necessity is the reason for the development of industries, crafts, businesses, and trade. Even before Islam, the region of Hijaz was famous for international trade, as evidenced by the mention of Quraysh's trade caravans in the Quran¹⁴. Islam also regards this profession with great esteem. Although the Prophet (PBUH) himself engaged in this profession, the need to correct it was essential just as many other areas of life had been corrupted before Islam. As it is stated about Jews' domination on all markets of Medina and their misuse of that power, Therefore He (PBUH) established new market to prevent this exploitation¹⁵ and the reforms in the business sector introduced by Him (PBUH) were bilateral, i.e., from both the buyer's and seller's perspectives. However, in the first stage, He (PBUH) prioritized the protection of merchants' rights. The initiatives taken in this regard are as follows:

Decisive Price Freely from the Balanced Supply and Demand

HE (PBUH) established a completely free market system in which there were no restrictions on the driving of goods that what should be produced? Or what should be imported and brought in? It was up to the trader's own interests and preferences. The determination of prices occurs at the equilibrium level of supply and demand. Once in

¹⁴ Al Qur'an, 106

¹⁵ Al Samhudi, Ali bin Abdullah, Wafa-ul-Wafa be Akhbar-e-Mustafa (Mtbatul- Ādāb wālmu'īd, Eygept, 1908) 540.

Medina, there was a shortage of grain, leading to a significant increase in prices. Some companions requested price controls, but He (PBUH) forbade it. Despite the fact that governments in those times would regulate prices in such situations, He (PBUH) refrained from it, considering the seller's loss.¹⁶

Prevention of Buying and Selling Outside the Market

In Medina, it was common for the people to gather before the arrival of trade caravans and, taking advantage of their unfamiliarity and exoticism, purchase goods at a lower price from the market. This practice, known as forestalling, and spreading false rumors to buy goods from the market at a lower price were common. He (PBUH) prohibited this to protect the interests of the seller and prevent its incidence.¹⁷

Promotion of Buying and Selling in the Market

The Jews were wealthy, and they had control over all four markets of Medina. They imposed taxes on trade in these markets, which was detrimental to both buyers and sellers in the event of price increases. Islam ended this and proscribed trading outside the market, making the market the center of all economic activities.

Prevention of Barter Trade

In the period of prophet hood, barter trade was also widespread, such as exchanging dried dates for fresh dates or one type of goods for another. This method of trade was not only difficult but also disposed to exploitation by individuals who possessed the desired goods. He (PBUH) not only forbidden it but also deemed it equivalent to interest, by selling inferior goods for gold in return, thus commanding the grander products in the market.¹⁸

Use of Currency as a Medium of Exchange

In the State of Medina, the Dinar and Dirham were used as a means of exchange, which facilitated the convenience of both parties and the absence of non-payment, while also promoting trade and the appropriate use of capital according to the requirements of the situation. Traders were free to invest their capital in businesses according to current circumstances. This monetary system not only reduced the risks of traders but also controlled the influx of provisions according to the prevailing conditions.

Second stage

Business Ethics, Protection of Consumer Rights, and Promotion of Direct Trade

¹⁶ At-Tirmidhi, Abu 'Isā Muhammad ibn 'Isa , Al-Jami' al-Kabir (Sunan At-Tirmidhi), Bāab Ma Ja'a Fi Al-Tas'ir, Hadith :1313, (Beirut Dar al-Gharb al-Islami.).

¹⁷ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Kitāb al-Buyu', Babu al-Nahyi 'an Talqī al-Rukbān wa Anna Bay'ahu Mardūdun, ,Hadith :2161.

¹⁸ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Kitab al-Buyu', Babun: 'Idha Arāda Bay'a Tamrin bi-Tamrin Khayrin Minhu Hadith La Taf'al, Bi'i al-Jam'a bi al-Darāhim, Hadith : 2200.

For strengthening the market in the State of Medina, where the merchants' interests were well taken care of, and then the adherence to business ethics was also prescribed. Some of them are given below:

Preclusion of Forbidden & Prohibited Products Trade In Islam

Certainly, Islam is the religion of well-being, it strictly discouraged of illegal & prohibited products' trade, as such the understanding of good and evil in matters is the reason behind their sanctity and prohibition. Therefore in an Islamic state, trading of forbidden and lawfully prohibited items is not only rejected but deemed deplorable. During the time of the Prophet (PBUH), when the prohibition of alcohol was revealed, Muslim merchants poured out all the alcohol they possessed, even though it meant losing all their capital invested in it.

Declaration of Defects in Transactions

It is essential for the seller while finalizing a deal to reveal upon others the defects of his products because it not only does the benefit the buyer, but it also strengthens the integrity of the trader, fostering mutual prosperity and blessing in economic affairs. Before the Prophet's prophet hood, His (PBUH) honesty in business dealings with Hazrat Khadijah R.A led to numerous benefits.¹⁹

Avoidance of false Oaths

Islam mandates truthfulness and transparency in trade as a truthful trader holds a high status. Speaking lies and making false promises to intimidate the customer is a major sin and leads to a lack of blessings. Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) said, "Deals may be finalized by lies, but blessings remain lost."²⁰

Failure to declare defects in goods and resorting to fraudulent practices obstruct the buyer from reckoning the true worth of the item, leading to dishonest transactions that result in a loss for the buyer as well as shambles the trader's integrity. For this in Arabic a term *Khalaaba* is used which means to sell everything that glitters as gold. In today's era, advertising is included in this term.

After a Buyer undergoes a Blackout, the Option of Cancelling a Purchase

Sometime despite of lacking purchasing power, a person buys something gratuitously, only to regret it later or making a purchase based on false estimates and incorrect assumptions. However, upon realizing the truth later, if he does not want to keep it, Islam grants the option of contract cancellation. The Prophet (PBUH) has contracted the buyer the option to cancel the sale of an animal whose udders have been snarled to stop

¹⁹ Ibn e Hisham, Abdul Rahman bin Abdullah bin Ahmad bin Abi al-Hasan al-Khath'ami al-Sahili, *Al-Sirah Al-Nabawiyah*, (Beirut Dar al-Kitab al-Arabi 1990), 01/ 212.

²⁰ Al Bukhari, *Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih*, *Kitab al-Buyu'*, Babu Ma Yukrahu Minal Halifi Fil Bay', Hadith :2087.

milk production²¹. This same facility is provided to consumers by the Consumer Rights Directive issued by the European Union in 2011²².

Sale of Non-Existent and Extinct Items

Islam is a religion of peace and sanctuary; it does not permit any action that may lead to dishonesty, deception, or harm to anyone. Therefore, the sale of non-existent and extinct items is not permitted. For instance, in Arabia, there was a practice of selling the unborn foal of a pregnant she-camel. This type of sale was uncertain, and the buyer was not assured any profit. Therefore, He (PBUH) prohibited it.²³ Similarly, selling fruit on a tree was only deemed permissible when it became ripe, as in the early stage, obtaining the fruit was uncertain.

Selling without Seeing or Touching (Mulamasah and Munabaza)

Selling clothes only by touching without seeing them, known as tactile selling (Mulamasah)²⁴, or throwing a stone to signify a sale, known as symbolic selling (Munabaza),²⁵ was a common practice. In such cases, there was a high possibility of deception and mutual animosity, so it was deemed impermissible.²⁶

Sale of Possession without Ownership and without Relocation

The Islamic trade system has been organized in such a way that both the seller and the buyer can benefit the most from their income and capital. Therefore, selling any goods without taking possession and without transferring them is not permissible because in this way, individual or even several individuals easily gain profits without investing, which adds to inflation. That's why even commission agents are prohibited too.²⁷

Adherence to Market Prices

The economic stability of a country largely depends on its market and the stability of prices in the market is a sign of economic progress. Sometimes fluctuations in prices affects the economy, but sometimes traders, for personal gain, sell goods at lower prices in the market. This practice destabilizes the strength of demand and supply in the market and leads to negative effects on the market. Therefore, baseless cheapness has been

²¹ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Kitab al-Buyu', Babu 'In Sha'a Radd al-Musarrat wa Fi Halbatih Sa'un Min Tamrin, Hadith : 2097

²² Commission notice ,Guidance on the interpretation and application of Directive 2011/83/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on consumer rights,(Text with EEA relevance), Official Journal of the European Union,p54 , <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021XC1229%2804%29#> (Accessed on 26-10-2024)

²³ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Babu bay'i al-gharar wa-habl al-hablati Hadith nahya 'un bay'i habl al-hablati, Hadith: 2143."

²⁴ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Babu bay'i al-Mulamasah wa-qāla Anas Naha 'Unhu an-Nabiyyu Sallallahu 'Alayhi wa sallam, Hadith :2143.

²⁵ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Babu bay'i al-Munabadhah wa-qaāla Anas naha 'Unhu an-Nabiyyu Sallallahu 'Alayhi wa sallam, Hadith: 2145.

²⁶ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Babu bay'i al-gharar wa-habl al-hablati Hadith naha 'Un Bay'i habl al-hablati, Hadith : 2142.

²⁷ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Babun: La yYshari Hādhirun Libadin bil-samsarati, Hadith :2159.

prohibited in the Islamic state. During the caliphate of Hazrat Umar(R.A) a trader used to sell goods at lower prices in the market. He was told to either follow the market or leave it.

Prohibition of Unnecessary Bidding

In the Islamic market, bidding was prohibited for those who had no intention to buy because it leads to price inflation.²⁸

Prohibition of Hoarding

Price fluctuations in the market is natural, but when hoarding is barred, prices rise incessantly, which affects the consumer and distillates wealth. Therefore, it has been prohibited.

Accountability System

The role of the government in economic stability is decisive and crucial. The government prepares a methodical code of conduct to conserve social, moral, and economic balance. This includes the establishment of an effective accountability system. This institution not only prevents activities that harm the morals and society but also addresses all actions within the market that have negative effects on the economy and society.

Fourteen hundred years ago, Islam laid down the principles of market rights. Today, Western thinkers are presenting it in modern terms. Hersh Shefrin and Mier Statman have mentioned the virtues of financial markets, all of which were present in the Islamic market.²⁹

Third stage

Prohibition of Interest

Interest is an increase that the creditor receives in return for granting a loan. Capital is an important factor in both Islamic and non-Islamic economies, but there is a big difference between both systems regarding its exchange, which has completely opposite effects. In the non-Islamic economy, capital exchange is interest, which is received at an agreed and fixed rate, whether it is for business purposes or to fulfill personal needs. Then, whether the business is profitable or loss-making, the capitalist receives interest. This interest-based system was rampant during the time of the Prophet Muhammad, (PBUH) where Jewish capitalists lent money on interest. Due to their control over the market, it was impossible to obliterate this interest-based system in the early days of Medina. Therefore, gradual reforms were made in the market as first to brace the economic condition of Muslims and then to eradicate the influence of Jews, followed by the pronouncement of the ultimate prohibition of interest.

30 وَأَحَلَّ اللَّهُ الْبَيْعَ وَحَرَّمَ الرِّبَا³⁰ “ God hath permitted trade and forbidden usury.”

²⁸ Al Bukhari, Al-Jāmi' Al-Sahih, Babun: La Yabi'u 'alā Bay'i akhihi walā Yasumu 'ala Sumi Akhihi Hetta Yadhana lāhu aw Yatruka, Hadith :2138.

²⁹ Sherfin, H, Ethics, Fairness and Efficiency in Financial Market, Financial Analyst ,journal 46,(6)

³⁰ Al Qur'an, 02 : 275

The capitalist and participatory system burdens capital on the real sector, which is the actual productive sector, making it extremely susceptible and causing crises in the economy³¹. On the other hand, Islam attaches capital continuously to business and makes its exchange dependent on profit and loss. Although the purpose of investing in business is to obtain financial benefits, its exchange is based on profit and loss instead of interest. The stock market is one form of this practice. The principles applied in Islamic banking today are based on these principles of non-interest. Whether it is direct or indirect taxation, a standard measure of value is required to determine the value of capital. In the interest-based system, this work is done through interest, and the rate of interest determines savings and investment. However, in the current Islamic banking system, this measure is based on real benefits. Therefore, capital does not exceed a certain limit in debt. Thus, Islamic economy cannot affect the real sector of the economy, and after achieving success, the economic crises faced by the non-Islamic system are avoided by the Islamic economy. The issue of interest is completely opposite to this³². Islam supports the circulation of wealth, while interest leads to the stagnation and concentration of capital.

5. The Role of State

In the economic system of Islam, from generating to the distribution of wealth, government endorses an important role. It is the responsibility of an Islamic state to certify and ensure that how wealth is generated? Who should consume it? What would be the criteria for determining their compensation, and how it should fairly be distributed among members of society?

Basically, the Islamic economic system does not validate either any of the Capitalist system of free economy or a Socialist system of collectivism. Instead, it allows for freedom in the production and consumption of goods and services within certain limits. The generation of wealth is subject to Islamic teachings of what is lawful and unlawful. It is the responsibility of an Islamic state to enforce these teachings and not permit the production of prohibited items such as alcohol, gambling, interest-based transactions and immoral activities like brothel.

Islam also provides guidance on how and where money should be spent. It prioritizes spending money on necessities and encourages avoiding extravagance and waste.

وَكُلُوا وَاشْرَبُوا وَلَا تُسْرِفُوا ۚ إِنَّهُ لَا يُحِبُّ الْمُسْرِفِينَ³³

“Eat and drink: but waste not by excess for God loveth not the wasters.”

³¹ In the form of profits, the exchange of capital is higher with other capitalists, which is detrimental to the economy. In 2014, French economist Thomas Piketty demonstrated through the statistics of developed countries over two centuries that the exchange of capital as profits, especially interest, is much higher with other capitalists, hindering economic production.

³² Greek economist Costas Lapavitsas has given the name "Profiting without Producing" to Usurious capitalism.

³³ Al Qur'an, 07 : 31

An Islamic state not only encourages individuals to follow these teachings but also sets an example by adhering to them. The life of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) serves as the best model in this regard.

In Islamic system, benefiting from the wealth of others is permitted under certain circumstances. This can happen either when someone is struck by a sudden calamity and needs financial assistance, or when someone uses someone else's capital for business purposes. In both cases, there is no room for interest (riba) in Islam. In the first scenario, wealth is not used as capital, and Islam offers two solutions: spending in the way of Allah (infaq fi sabillillah) or providing an interest-free loan (qardh e hasan). An example from the Prophet's era is the pact of brotherhood between the Ansar and the Muhajirun, where the Ansar spent in the way of Allah and also provided interest-free loans for the welfare of the community³⁴. The second scenario is a business loan. Although the purpose of investing in business is to gain financial benefit, the return is based on profit and loss instead of interest, and it involves risk-taking. With the establishment of Islamic banking in today's advanced world, many interest-free transactions have become common. It is the duty of an Islamic government to promote Islamic banking and strive to eliminate the interest-based system, which has been preserved for centuries since the time of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH).

Surprisingly, whether it's a capitalist system or collectivism, both agree that economic development is only possible when capital is used for productive purposes. However, the biggest problem of today's world is free capital, and its failure to be incorporated into any system is hindering the establishment of a sustainable economy.

6. Foreign Policy

Internal political stability, strong friendly and prudent relationships with neighbor states and sagacious strategy always lead to sustainable economic development and long term prosperity. Therefore, Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) besides aforementioned measures in Medina state for economic stability, focused on foreign policy and ensured not only political solidity, indemnity of peace but also for economic immovability and these measures were enhanced affectively by the succession of agreements with the southwestern tribes of Medina, these agreements began in 2 Hijri. These agreements were thru with the tribes living in the southwest of Medina, including the tribes of Juhina, Ashjaja, Bnū Madalaj, Bnū Damra, Bnū mzīna and Bnū Ghfār. The summary of all these agreements was based on such rapports that, none of these tribes will be a part of any war against the Muslims and will also assist each other against the persecutor and oppressor. Some tribes also agreed to remain neutral and nonaligned.³⁵ The defense of Medina became stronger and the Muslim control over the Syrian trade route enlarged.

³⁴ Ibn e Hisham ,Al-Sirah al-Nabawiyyah, 2/146

³⁵ Hameed Ullah, Muhammad, Dr., majmū'ata aḥwathāyiqi aḥsāyāsātī liil'ahda aḥnābawīa wa aḥlḥaff alrāshidatā ,(dāra aḥnfaḥs , byrwt ,1987), 262-293.

7. Ethical Teachings

In addition to economic reforms, the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) also emphasized the ethical upbringing of the people of Islam, with key points including:

Encouragement of Moderation

The inclination towards moderation in every aspect of life³⁶, leaving luxuries and focusing on necessities and essentials, not only affects the personal finances of an individual but also has positive effects on the lives of other members of society.

Prevention of Extravagance

Allah is the real owner of wealth; ³⁷ *لِلَّهِ مُلْكُ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ ط* “To God belongs the dominion Of the heavens and the earth.”

Men have been entrusted with it in this world and are permitted to use it in worldly life. However, Islam does not allow the waste of resources, whether it be extravagance or wastefulness, as it is a trust and its excess is the infraction of the rights of other individuals.

Encouragement of Spending In The Way Of Allah

In non-Islamic economic systems, the entire dependence of the government on taxes is based on the collection of revenues, while in Islam the imposition of taxes is only permissible in times of disaster. As an alternative, Islam emphasizes giving Zakat as an act of adoration for the welfare of the public, along with voluntary charity and spending in the path of Allah. Payment of taxes is considered an encumbrance and an infliction by the public whereas Zakat and almsgiving are thru with the purpose of fulfilling a religious obligation and seeking rewards. Thus, its collection is easier compared to taxes. Furthermore, Allah has also mentioned its disbursements, so its distribution is more effective and based on social welfare and justice. To achieve social, ethical, and economic balance, the Islamic government has adopted a three-pronged policy:

- Commercial reforms
- Prohibition of interest
- Ethical education

By adopting these policies, the state strengthens its economic credibility, making public happiness and sustainable development achievable.

8. The Contemporary Economic Instability and The Prophetic Strategy

While some Western intellectuals highlight the success of various ingenuities and initiatives of Islamic policy, it is also true that in this cogent and rational age, the economic system of the state of Madinah is not considered credible because of the simple life of that

³⁶ Ahmad bin Hanbal, al-Musnad ,Musnad al-Mukthireen min al-Sahabah, Musnad Abdullah ibn Mas'ood, radi Allahu 'anhu,, Hadith: 4269.

³⁷ Al Qur'an, 42: 49

time and today's economic problems are different. At that time, it was beneficial, but today, the system's functioning is not correct. The rejection of the benefits of Islamic teachings is not a valid argument; instead, attention should be paid to the issues that are prevalent worldwide today, including:

- Unlimited expansion of economic efforts
- Dominance of the financial sector over the real sector
- Weakness of government institutions
- Concentration of wealth
- Unethical behavior in trade

These are the same issues that surrounded the prodigious governments and remarkable empires of that time. The reforms inaugurated by the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) to the Worlds at that time and the foundation of a strong economy are still beacons of light. While it can lead to the advancement of human life and cultural change, the core issues remain the same.

9. Conclusion

To conclude it is seen that how the economic instability is currently the world's largest issue, affecting humanity with excessive wealth disparity, unemployment, economic stagnation, accompanying with political, social, and psychological challenges. Despite the efforts of global economic experts to find solutions, the remedies they propose often provide only temporary relief, and advancements in modern technology sometimes intensify and worsen economic crunches and crisis.

In essence, the systems introduced by human intellect only address surface-level problems, while Islam provides a comprehensive and perpetual guidance covering all spectrums and aspects of life. Its unique economic theory fulfills the demands of every era and of every time Islam offers an all-inclusive set of principles that certify and ensure the stability of not just individuals but the entire societal system. Just as it brought about a revolution in the Arab society fourteen centuries ago, the Prophetic policy remains equally operative and effective today. However, by adhering to these principles, Pakistan and other developing states which are facing such economic issues, can take steps towards economic stability that could diminish and mitigate present uncertainties by paving the way for progress.

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